

Supplementary Material 1. Search Strategies

MEDLINE (via Pubmed) was searched from inception to September 2023 using the following search strategy:

- #1. nephrolithiasis[MESH]
- #2. “kidney calculi”[MESH]
- #3. “kidney calculus”[Title/Abstract]
- #4. “renal calculus”[Title/Abstract]
- #5. “renal calculi”[Title/Abstract]
- #6. “kidney stones”[Title/Abstract]
- #7. "kidney stone"[Title/Abstract]
- #8. #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7
- #9. "nephrolithotomy, percutaneous"[MESH]
- #10. PCNL[Text Word]
- #11. PNL[Text Word]
- #12. nephrolitho*[tiab]
- #13. #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12
- #14. #8 AND #13
- #15. #8 AND #13 Filters: Meta Analysis, Systematic Review

The Cochrane Library (via Wiley) was searched from inception to September 2023 on 01 September 2023 using the following search strategy:

- #1. MeSH descriptor: [Nephrolithiasis] this term only
- #2. MeSH descriptor: [Kidney Calculi] this term only
- #3. (“kidney calculus”):ti,ab,kw
- #4. (“renal calculus”):ti,ab,kw
- #5. (“renal calculi”):ti,ab,kw
- #6. (“kidney stone*”):ti,ab,kw

#7. #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6.

#8 MeSH descriptor: [Nephrolithotomy, Percutaneous] this term only

#9. (PCNL):ti,ab,kw

#10. (PNL):ti,ab,kw

#11. (nephrolitho*):ti,ab,kw

#12. #8 OR #9 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11

#13. #7 AND #12 in Cochrane Reviews

VIRTUAL LIBRARY IN HEALTH (LILACS) was searched from inception to September 2023 on 01 September 2023 using the following search strategy:

("Cálculos Renales" OR nephrolithiasis OR nefrolitiasis OR "Kidney Calculi") AND ("nephrolithotomy, percutaneous" OR "Nefrolitotomía Percutánea" OR pcnl OR pnl) AND (type_of_study:(("systematic_reviews")))

EPISTEMONIKOS was searched from inception to September 2023 on 01 September 2023 using the following search strategy and filter by publication type systematic review:

Full query: (title:((title:(nephrolithiasis) OR abstract:(nephrolithiasis)) OR (title:(kidney calcul*) OR abstract:(kidney calcul*)) OR (title:(renal calcul*) OR abstract:(renal calcul*)) OR (title:(kidney stones) OR abstract:(kidney stones))) OR abstract:((title:(nephrolithiasis) OR abstract:(nephrolithiasis)) OR (title:(kidney calcul*) OR abstract:(kidney calcul*)) OR (title:(renal calcul*) OR abstract:(renal calcul*)) OR (title:(kidney stones) OR abstract:(kidney stones)))) AND (title:((title:("mini perc") OR abstract:("mini perc")) OR (title:("ultra mini perc") OR abstract:("ultra mini perc")) OR (title:("micro perc") OR abstract:("micro perc")) OR (title:("mini micro perc") OR abstract:("mini micro perc")) OR (title:("mini PCNL") OR abstract:("mini PCNL")) OR (title:("ultramini PCNL") OR abstract:("ultramini PCNL")) OR (title:("micro PCNL") OR abstract:("micro PCNL")) OR (title:("mini micro PCNL") OR abstract:("mini micro PCNL")) OR (title:("retrograde intrarenal surgery") OR abstract:("retrograde intrarenal surgery")) OR (title:(RIRS) OR abstract:(RIRS)) OR (title:("flexible ureterosco*") OR abstract:("flexible ureterosco*")) OR (title:("extracorporeal shockwave litho*") OR abstract:("extracorporeal shockwave litho*")) OR (title:(ESWL) OR abstract:(ESWL)) OR (title:(Laparoscopic pyelolithotomy) OR abstract:(Laparoscopic pyelolithotomy))))